

doi.org/10.4038/jccpsl.v31i5.8864

JCCPSL

Journal of College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka

Volume 31 - August 2025 Special Issue

Global Public Health Summit 2025

30th Annual Academic Sessions of the
College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka

Abstracts of Oral and Poster Presentations

13th to 16th of July 2025
Colombo, Sri Lanka

GPHS 2025
Colombo, Sri Lanka

Appropriateness of antiplatelet prescriptions and its unwarranted impact on institutional pharmaceutical budget in a primary healthcare setting in Sri Lanka

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Background: Recent guideline updates have refined the indications for antiplatelet therapy to optimise patient care. Inappropriate prescriptions of antiplatelets are a health risk for patients and cause unnecessary financial burden on the healthcare system.

Aims: To assess the appropriateness of antiplatelet prescriptions and their unwarranted impact on the institutional pharmaceutical budget in a primary healthcare setting in Sri Lanka

Methods: A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted in the outpatient medical clinic of a primary medical care unit (PMCU) in Sri Lanka. Records of all patients followed up from January to December 2023 were evaluated. Records of patients lost to follow up, deceased and transferred/discharged from the clinic during the study period were excluded. Data extraction sheets were used to extract data from patient records, annual pharmaceutical estimate, stock transfer vouchers and drug stores register. The 2019 American Heart Association/American College of Cardiology guidelines was used as the reference.

Results: Sixty one out of 234 clinic patients were on antiplatelet therapy. Of those on antiplatelets, 80% were females. Median age was 74 years and 90% were ≥ 65 years. Most (60.7%) were on antiplatelets for secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease. A 57.4% was on inappropriate prescriptions, mainly for primary prevention (68.6%). Nearly 53% of the budget allocated for antiplatelets was spent on inappropriate prescriptions.

Conclusions: Gaps in translating guidelines to practice and lack of medication review may have caused inappropriate prescription of antiplatelet agents placing patients at undue health risks while posing a financial risk to the healthcare system.

Key words: Antiplatelet therapy, Medication review, Guideline recommendations, High bleeding risk

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